
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS ENHANCEMENT TOOL FOR WELDING TECHNICIANS ON IMPROVING WELD JOINTS FOR QUALITY JOBS

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ABSTRACT

Weld defects reduce structural strength, integrity, and reliability, leading to failures, reduced performance, and safety hazards for end-users. Inclusion of AI systems in welding processes aids in eliminating weld defects as well as improving jobs quality. This study investigated Artificial Intelligence as Enhancement Tool for Welding Technicians on Improving Weld Joints for Quality Jobs. This study used descriptive survey research design. The area of the study was, Benue State of Nigeria. The population of the study was 1600. A sample of 48 welding technicians was selected using Purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection for this study was a self-structured questionnaire titled Artificial Intelligence Enhancement tool for Quality Jobs (AIETQJ) and was validated by 3 experts in varying disciplines. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was computed and the results obtained yielded a reliability coefficient alpha (α) values of; 0.85, and 0.83. Two research questions guided the study. Mean scores was used to answer the research questions and the standard deviation was used to check spread of the mean scores among the respondents. The mean scores and standard deviation were calculated using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. The mean response were weighed with real limit of numbers as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 (3.50-4.00), Agree (A) = 3 (2.50- 3.49), Disagree (D) = 2 (1.00-2.49) and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 (0.50-1.49). The items with mean scores between 0.50 to 1.49 were considered Strongly Disagree, items with mean scores between 1.50 to 2.49 were considered Disagree, items with mean scores between 2.50 to 3.49 were considered Agree and items with mean scores between 3.50 to 4.00 were considered strongly Agree. The researcher distributed the 48 copies of AIETQJ questionnaires to the respondents and only 44 copies of AIETQJQ were returned. The null hypothesis formulated was tested using Chi-square and decisions were taken based on P-values and Alpha values. When $P < 0.5$, the null hypothesis was rejected and considered significant and when $P > 0.5$, the

null hypothesis was not rejected and considered not significant. The study concludes that AI is a groundbreaking technology and makes it the reason why a growing number of production and manufacturing companies have integrated it in their businesses to improve practices with good quality jobs, make better decisions, and build emerging technologies. Application of AI systems in welding processes will solve many problems including weld defects and other related issues affecting jobs quality. It recommends that welding technicians should try as much as they could to prevent weld defects on their finished jobs. Welding Technicians must prepare joints properly (clean, fit-up), select the right materials and equipment. The study also recommends integration of AI systems in welding process for optimum productivity.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Enhancement, Welding Technicians, weld Joints Quality Jobs.*

INTRODUCTION

Several years back, many welding technicians especially those in Nigeria usually perform weld joints that were seemingly not of good quality leading to unjustifiable technical errors which could lead to waste of resources, time and energy in the field of work. However, in recent years, the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) in the field of work has made unprecedented advancement in the area of fabrication and welding improving weld joints with precision and accuracy. Artificial intelligence (AI) according to Du-Haper, Watt, Luscombe and Lynch (2020) is difficult to define, yet refers to it as the “ability of a machine to communicate, reason and operate independently in both familiar and novel scenarios in a similar manner to a human”. Alan Turing’s 1950 article titled Computing Machinery and Intelligence discussed conditions for considering a machine to be intelligent. He argued that if the machine could successfully pretend to be human to a knowledgeable observer then you certainly should consider it intelligent (McCarthy, 2021). Stryker (2024) averred that Artificial intelligence (AI) is technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision making, creativity and autonomy. Stryker insisted that applications and devices equipped with AI can see and identify objects. They can understand and respond to human language. Such objects incorporated with AI can also learn from new information and experience. They can make detailed recommendations to users and experts. AI can act

independently, replacing the need for human intelligence or intervention which can be seen on self-welding machines.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) could also be seen as trans-human technology that fundamentally enhances longevity by technically reducing construction error and human cognitive overload, aiming at transcending present human constraints and evolve into post human. Artificial Intelligence (AI) being an enhancement tool in the world of work can be utilized by welding technicians in carrying out welding jobs effectively. Cambridge Dictionary (n.d.) defines enhancement as the process of improving the quality, amount, or strength of something. While Vocabulary.com (n.d.) defines tool as an instrument that helps someone to accomplish some task. It can also be referred to as an object that can extend an individual's ability to modify features of the surrounding environment or help them accomplish a particular task. Using AI technology to perform welding jobs will definitely help improve precision, efficiency, and safety.

Welding is a process that fuses two or more materials, typically metals, by using heat, pressure, or both. This creates a permanent bond known as a weldment, and the original pieces being joined are called the parent materials. The material added to help form the weld is known as a filler or consumable. Welding is used in manufacturing, repair, and fabrication across a wide range of industries. Some people would say welding is an art form since some materials require specific processes or techniques (Erie Institute of Technology, 2022). Welding is a fabrication process that fuses two or more materials, most commonly metals and thermoplastics, by applying heat, pressure, or both to create a permanent bond. The materials are heated to their melting points and mixed, often with the addition of a filler material (a type of electrode or rod), to form a single, unified piece. This process creates a strong, integrated joint, referred to as a weldment, and is used across various industries like manufacturing, construction, and automotive. Therefore, welding technician who has received enough theoretical and practical training in welding either formally or informally and acquired the necessary work skills in different method and techniques of welding ought to utilize AI in welding processes. The American Welding Society (2020) found that welding technicians use their extensive knowledge of joining processes, materials, welding equipment, welding techniques, and standards to assist welding engineering personnel with the development, application, evaluation, and documentation of welding

techniques, equipment, and processes used to manufacture welded products according to relevant codes.

Welding technicians in Nigeria willing to carry out fabrication jobs that can stand the test of time, will as a matter of importance integrate AI in their welding processes for quality jobs that will be free from welding defects. Welding Defects can be referred to as the irregularities formed in the given weld metal due to wrong welding process parameters or incorrect welding patterns (Saadat & Wajahat, 2019). The defects may differ from the desired weld bead shape, size, and intended quality. Welding defects may occur from either outside or inside of the weldment. Some of the defects may be allowed if the defects are under permissible limits but other defects such as cracks, porosity, and improper penetration are never accepted. Incorrect procedure or poor technique may produce weld defects leading to premature failure in service (Nisith, 2016). AI-driven welding systems optimize welding parameters, such as voltage, speed, and feed rate. These kind of precision results can often produce higher-quality welds with fewer defects, reducing the need for rework on the welder side in other words, helps reduce human error (College of Eastern Idaho, 2024). Professional Technicians Training Institute (PTT, 2024) insists that AI integration in welding can adapt to various environments, ensuring consistent quality even in challenging conditions such as underwater welding, joining liquid containers, gas cylinders and pressure pipes. AI-powered welding systems can analyze real-time data and make minute adjustments during the welding process. This ensures consistent quality and reduces the risk of human error. Plus, automated welding robots that use AI can deliver repeatable welds. AI can use predictive analytics to identify potential equipment failures before they occur. This minimizes downtime and ensures welding tools are operating properly. Similarly, AI can inspect weld quality in real time, using machine vision and sensors to detect defects for enhanced quality control. By automating dangerous welding tasks, AI reduces human exposure to the hazards of the job. Welding robots that use AI can handle tasks in extreme conditions, such as underwater or high-temperature environments, improving workplace safety (Refrigeration School, Inc., 2025).

In as much as Artificial Intelligence (AI) is an everyday common tool that is now transforming industries worldwide, welding and fabrication is no exception, it also presents challenges that need careful consideration from human bodies. Some of the challenges according to College of Eastern

Idaho (2024), are that implementing AI in welding requires significant technical expertise. Businesses must invest in training for their workforce to manage and maintain these advanced systems. The complexity of AI algorithms and the need for ongoing updates and troubleshooting can also pose challenges. Companies need to ensure that their staff are well-equipped to handle these new technologies to maximize their benefits. AI systems in welding are usually connected to networks for data analysis and remote monitoring. This connectivity exposes the system to cyber security risks, such as hacking and data breaches, which can compromise the integrity of welding processes and sensitive company information. The effectiveness of AI in welding heavily depends on the quality of the data fed into the systems. Poor-quality or incomplete data can lead to sub-optimal performance, errors, and even failures in the welding process. Ensuring that AI systems have access to accurate, comprehensive data is essential for their success. This requirement can be challenging, as it involves continuous data collection, management, and validation.

A highly trained professional welding technician who support welding operations with inspection, testing, troubleshooting, and technical documentation requires artificial intelligence for optimum performance. Many welding technicians do accomplished many task without integrating AI in to the system. However, in most cases such tasks possess a lot of technical errors leading to welding defects such as cracks, porosity, undercut, slag inclusion, spatter, overlap, incomplete fusion and incomplete penetration (Saadat & Wajahat, 2019). To address the lingering weld defects problem, the study sought to find out the system adopted by welding technicians to eliminate such weld defects, making the job a quality one. Specifically the study determine whether;

1. jobs handled by welding technicians still suffer some weld defects in Benue state;
2. welding technicians adopts AI measures to eliminate weld defects in Benue state;

Research Questions

Three research questions were raised and answered.

1. What are the weld defects still affecting finished jobs in Benue state?
2. What are the AI measures adopted by welding technicians to eliminate weld defects in Benue state?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between weld jobs finished with AI system applications and those finished without AI systems applications.

Research Methods

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of the study was 1600 welding technicians. Purposive sampling technique was used to sample only the 44 welding technicians that owns standard fabrication/welding workshops and also registered members of the Welders Association of Nigeria, Benue state chapter as respondents. The respondent were selected from various registers of the welders association in six major towns (Zaki-Biam, Katsina-Ala, Gboko, Makurdi, Otukpo and Otukpa). The instrument used for data collection for this study was a self-structured questionnaire titled Artificial Intelligence Enhancement tool for Quality Jobs (AIETQJ). The AIETQJ questionnaire instrument was validated by 3 experts in varying disciplines and was subjected to reliability analysis using the test of internal consistency. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was computed and the results obtained yielded a reliability coefficient alpha (α) values of; 0.85, 0.79, and 0.83. Mean scores was used to answer the research questions and the standard deviation was used to check spread of the mean scores among the respondents. The mean scores and standard deviation were calculated using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21. The mean response were weighed with real limit of numbers as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 (3.50-4.00), Agree (A) = 3 (2.50- 3.49), -3.49), Disagree (D) = 2 (1.00-2.49) and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 (0.50-1.49). The items with mean scores between 0.50 to 1.49 were considered Strongly Disagree, items with mean scores between 1.50 to 2.49 were considered Disagree, items with mean scores between 2.50 to 3.49 were considered Agree and items with mean scores between 3.50 to 4.00 were considered strongly Agree. The researcher distributed the 366 copies of AIETQJ questionnaires to the respondents and only 360 copies of AIETQJQ were returned. The null hypothesis formulated was tested using Chi-square and decisions were taken based on P-values and Alpha values. When $P < 0.5$, the null hypothesis was rejected and considered significant and when $P > 0.5$, the null hypothesis was not rejected and considered not significant.

Results

Table 1: Mean ratings of the responses of Welding Technicians about the weld defects on finished jobs.

S/N	Item statement	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1	My weld joints are free from cracks.	2.16	0.09	Disagree
2	My weld joints are free from porosity.	1.70	0.63	Disagree
3	My weld joints are free from undercut.	1.75	0.43	Disagree
4	My weld joints are free from slag inclusion.	2.27	0.73	Disagree
5	My weld joints are free from spatter.	1.57	0.59	Disagree
6	My weld joints are free from overlap.	2.05	0.75	Disagree
7	My weld joints are free from incomplete fusion.	2.05	0.93	Disagree
8	My weld joints are free from incomplete penetration.	2.11	0.89	Disagree
	Cluster Mean	2.01		Disagree

Table 1 revealed that the Welding technicians disagree on all the 8 listed items with mean responses ranging from 1.57 to 2.16 as weld defects still noticed on finished jobs fabricated by Welding Technicians in Benue state. The cluster mean of 2.01 indicates that the respondents completely agree of their finished product having wed defects. The standard deviations displayed show level of homogeneity among the respondents which implies consensus of opinions.

Table 2: Mean ratings of the responses of Welding Technicians about the application of AI measures Systems to eliminate weld defects on finished jobs.

S/N	Item statement	\bar{X}	S D	Remarks
9	Real time analysis.	1.57	0.58	Disagree
10	Parameter adjustment.	1.96	0.75	Disagree
11	Feedback loops.	1.80	0.63	Disagree
12	Computer vision system.	1.57	0.59	Disagree
13	Pattern recognition.	2.09	0.77	Disagree
14	Troubleshooting.	2.66	0.53	Agree
15	Job inspection.	2.77	0.80	Agree
	Cluster mean	2.05		Disagree

Table 2 revealed that Welding technicians disagree on 5 of the 7 listed items with mean responses ranging from 1.57 to 2.09 and agree on 2 of the items with mean responses ranging between 2.66 and 2.77. The cluster mean of 2.05 deduces that the Welding Technicians do not fully integrate

AI systems in their welding processes. The standard deviations as indicated show level of homogeneity among the respondents which implies consensus of opinions.

Table 3: Chi-Square test of the AI system application by Welding Technicians to eliminate weld defects on finished jobs

	Observed N	Expected N	Df	X ² Cal	Sig	Remark
Finished jobs without AI system application	42	22.0	1	36.36 ^a	0.000	Significant
Finished jobs with AI system applications	2	22.0				
Total	44					

Key: Df, Degree of freedom, X² Cal = to Chi-Square calculated, Sig. =P-value

Table 3 shows the Chi-Square calculated value of 36.36, Degree of freedom (df) = 3 and Sig. (p-value = 0.00) which is less than the Alpha value (α) of 0.05 level of significance. Since $P < 0.5$, the null hypothesis was rejected and considered significant.

DISCUSSIONS

The findings with respect to research question one revealed that Welding Technicians carrying out fabrication works in Benue state still produced jobs that were having one weld defect or the other. The finding is in agreement with Nisith (2016), who concluded that there can be flaws in the welded joint, depending on their, size, location and type which may be considered as defects. Nisith insists that once these defects are detected, remedial measures are to be implemented to remove them, as because a structure cannot be put to service with defects. Flaws are nothing but imperfections in a welded joint. Welding procedure, joint features, access and welding technique will have direct effect on fabrication imperfections. The majority of the defects encountered in welded structures are primarily due to improper welding procedure. The findings is also in consonance with Professional Technicians Training Institute (PTT, 2024), who founds that AI integration in welding can adapt to various environments, ensuring consistent quality even in challenging conditions such as underwater welding, joining liquid containers, gas cylinders and pressure pipes. The findings also agrees with Saadat and

Wajahat (2019) who discovered that welding defects usually affect weld quality and longevity and advised that rejections of the weld structure on the basis of the welding defect should be minimized ensuring better means or measures of welding for quality works.

The findings of the study with respect to research question two and hypothesis one shows that Welding Technicians carrying out fabrication jobs in Benue state do not fully embrace artificial intelligence systems in their welding processes. Being one of the reasons why most of their finished fabrication works encountered weld defects such as cracks, porosity, undercut, slag inclusion, spatter, overlap, incomplete fusion and incomplete penetration. The agrees with that of Professional Technicians Training Institute (PTT, 2024), which emphasized that AI applications in welding can inspect weld quality in real time, using machine vision and sensors to detect defects for enhanced quality control. By automating dangerous welding tasks, AI reduces human exposure to the hazards of the job. The findings also agrees with that of Florence, Samsingh and Babureddy (2018), who found that weld defects have the potential to be dangerous as they might give rise to high stress intensities which may result in failure of the joint. Therefore, recommends AI systems of welding which is capable of identifying four major weld defects, namely lack of side-wall fusion, lack of weld penetration, slag inclusion and weld porosity and the presence of no defect as well.

Conclusion

No doubt, AI is a groundbreaking technology and makes it the reason why a growing number of production and manufacturing companies have integrated it in their businesses to improve practices with good quality jobs, make better decisions, and build emerging technologies. Application of AI systems in welding processes will solve many problems including weld defects and other related issues affecting jobs quality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommends that; welding technicians should try as much as they could to prevent weld defects on their finished jobs. Welding Technicians must prepare joints properly (clean, fit-up), select the right materials and equipment. The study also recommends integration of AI systems in welding process for optimum productivity.

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